

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Planting Awareness, Reaping Cleanliness: Community Empowerment Strategies in Waste Management

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Abstract

Community empowerment is necessary as a strategy to encourage communities to be independent in waste management. Community-based waste management is the foundation of waste management at the upstream level. This study aims to describe and analyze the extent to which community empowerment is carried out in waste management. The results of the study show that various community empowerment efforts are carried out by strengthening various community-based waste management facilities, such as: Waste Banks, 3R TPS, and so on.

Keywords: Community empowerment; Waste management; Community-based waste management

1. Introduction

Community empowerment is one of the key strategies in waste management. Community independence in waste management is necessary in order to preserve the environment and achieve sustainability, so community empowerment is needed as an effort to encourage this independence. Swift and Levin (Mardikanto, 2010) state that community empowerment aims to encourage communities, especially vulnerable, marginalized, and weak communities, to improve their capacity through the resources available in their environment.

Mardikanto & Soebianto (2015) wrote that empowerment is an effort to provide opportunities for marginalized communities to actively participate in development. This is done by encouraging them to be more active in various development programs. Najiyati, et al., (2005) emphasized that this participation is key to strengthening community independence. Wandersman et al. (2005) emphasize that this participation is an important factor in community empowerment. This participation is related to efforts to encourage community involvement in the decision-making process. This study aims to describe and analyze the extent to which community empowerment in waste management is carried out.

2. Discussion

2.1. Community Empowerment

Several experts have defined community empowerment from various perspectives. Crick (Azizy, 2003) writes that community empowerment is an effort to encourage marginalized communities to actively participate in the decision-making process. Furthermore, it is mentioned that community empowerment is a manifestation of the principles of democratization. Not only that, community empowerment is related to the implementation of public policy.

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Adimihardja and Hikmat (2001) wrote that community empowerment is a process of actualizing the potential that communities possess. Community empowerment can be carried out through an individual approach (individual self-empowerment) or a collective approach (collective self-empowerment). In line with this, Rakib & Syam (2016) write that community empowerment is an effort to facilitate communities so that they have opportunities to determine their lives through the optimization of the local organizations they participate in.

Mardikanto & Soebianto (2015) wrote that community empowerment is an effort to open opportunities for communities regarding their rights in decision-making. On the other hand, Zubaedi (2013) emphasizes that community empowerment is a process carried out to provide support for communities so that they have adequate capacity through a series of activities aimed at motivating them. This means that community empowerment is related to increasing their awareness of improving their abilities.

Payne (Masrukin, et al., 2014) defines community empowerment as efforts made to support communities so that they have power in the decision-making process. This process is greatly influenced by various factors, ranging from personal to social factors. Furthermore, this process is important in improving the capabilities of communities by maximizing their potential.

Alsop et al. (2006) define community empowerment as efforts to improve the ability of individuals and groups to make decisions independently. The capacity of individuals and groups to make effective choices is essential in the process of community empowerment. Furthermore, community empowerment is related to the process of translating these choices into actions that affect their lives.

Barnes (2020) defines empowerment as efforts to improve community capabilities through a series of programs (empowering program design), empowering relationships, and organizations that support them (empowering by organization). In line with this, the World Bank (Narayan, ed., 2002) states that community empowerment is the expansion of community assets and capabilities to actively participate in development. Furthermore, community empowerment is an effort to encourage vulnerable and weak communities to be able to negotiate, influence, have control and capacity in holding accountable the organizations that influence them.

Kartasasmita (Andriyani, et al., 2017) defines community empowerment as a process carried out to improve the dignity and status of the community. The aim of community empowerment is to give marginalized communities the freedom to escape poverty and backwardness. Similarly, Sumodiningrat (2007) states that community empowerment is an effort to facilitate communities in improving their capacity and to protect them from unhealthy competition in accessing productive resources that affect their lives.

Based on the various definitions of community empowerment mentioned by these experts, the following conclusions can be drawn. First, community empowerment is an effort to encourage the community's capacity for decision-making. Second, community empowerment is an effort to facilitate the community through local organizations that are expected to optimize their potential. Third, community empowerment is an effort to foster community awareness for the improvement of their standard of living.

2.2. Waste and Waste Management

Waste is the result of human activities, both at the household and industrial levels. Waste is solid material produced from industrial or household activities (Sandika, et al., 2018). On the other hand, Manik (Mansyur, 2021) writes that waste is an object produced from human activities, which is the result of industrial activities, including mining, agriculture, animal husbandry, fisheries, transportation, households, trade, and other human activities. Suyoto (2008) defines waste as the solid residue of human daily activities or natural processes.

Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 18 of 2008 concerning Waste Management defines waste management as systematic, comprehensive, and continuous activities that include waste reduction and handling. Sujarwo, et al (2014) define waste management as activities carried out to obtain benefits from the value of the waste itself. Furthermore, waste management is an activity carried out to avoid the adverse effects of waste on health and the surrounding environment.

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waste management is an activity carried out to avoid the adverse effects of waste on health and the surrounding environment.

Yudiyanto et al. (2019) wrote that waste management is a series of activities carried out to limit waste accumulation through various efforts, including waste recycling, with the aim of reusing the waste. Waste management is related to efforts made in handling waste. These efforts include: waste sorting, waste collection, waste transportation, waste processing, and final waste processing.

2.3. Community Empowerment in Waste Management

The volume of waste is increasing day by day. This is influenced by the lack of public awareness in applying the principles of Reduce, Reuse, and Recycle (3R). Reduce refers to efforts made to reduce waste. Reuse refers to the reuse of used items that are still usable. Recycle refers to efforts made to recycle waste so that it can be reused (Dwiyanto, 2011). The 3R principle can be implemented through a community empowerment approach. Community involvement in the implementation of the 3R principle is expected to increase the community's capacity in waste management.

The role of the community in environmental protection efforts is essential. This is because communities are required to have the capacity to solve problems related to their environment (Elamin, et al., 2018). Conditions in the field often show that community awareness of waste management is still low. Some communities manage waste by burning it. Ikhsandri (2014) writes that burning waste is one technique of waste management. However, it is often difficult to control the impact of this burning, as the smoke, dust, and charcoal from the waste have the potential to pollute the surrounding environment.

Several previous researchers have studied community empowerment in waste management. Mansyur (2021) conducted research on community empowerment in waste management in Banjarsari District, Surakarta City. The results of his research show that community empowerment needs to be strengthened by increasing the capacity of local organizations. Community empowerment efforts are carried out through the optimization of the Waste Bank. Asnifatima (2018) conducted research on Community Empowerment Through Household Waste Management in Cimanggu Satu Village. The results of her research show that community empowerment can encourage changes in community behavior in maintaining environmental cleanliness and waste management.

Al Ghani, et al. (2020) conducted research on Community Empowerment in the Management and Value Enhancement of Inorganic Waste in the Legoso Raya RT 001/001 Pisangan Ciputat Timur area. The results of their research show that community empowerment in waste management can be seen from the aspects of education, health, and economy. In terms of education, the community has knowledge and skills in making recycled waste products. In terms of health, the community environment is clean from waste. In terms of the economic aspect, the community's income increased in line with the sales of recycled waste craft products.

Muljono, et al (2024) through Community Empowerment Through Waste Management and Its Application in Everyday Life Towards Zero Waste in Pengejek Village, Jonggat District, Central Lombok. The results of the study show that community empowerment can increase community awareness, knowledge, and creativity in waste management. Community empowerment efforts are carried out through the optimization of 3R TPS (Waste Processing Site with the Principles of Reduce, Reuse, Recycle). The following are some previous studies related to community empowerment in waste management, as shown in Table 1:

Table 1 Research on Community Empowerment in Waste Management

No.	Research Title	Author	Year
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)
1.	Community Empowerment in Waste Management in Banjarsari District, Surakarta City	Mansyur	2021
2.	Community Empowerment in the Management and Enhancement of the Useful Value of Inorganic Waste in the Legoso Raya Area, RT 001/001, Pisangan, East Ciputat	Al Ghani, et al	2020
3.	Community Empowerment Through Household Waste Management in Cimanggu Satu Village	Asnifatima, et al	2018

4.	Community Empowerment Through Waste Management and Its Application in Everyday Life Towards Zero Waste in Pengejek Village, Jonggat District, Central Lombok	Muljono, et al	2014
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Source: Mansyur, 2021; Al Ghani, et al., 2020; Asnifatima, et al., 2018, Muljono, et a., 2014.

Previous studies show that community empowerment in waste management has been a topic of interest among researchers. Effective waste management can be achieved through community empowerment efforts. Conversely, community empowerment can be carried out in an effort to address issues surrounding waste.

Community-based waste management is very important. Active community involvement in maintaining the cleanliness of their environment is essential. Community involvement in waste management is expected to reduce the volume of waste disposed of in landfills. Ultimately, waste generation is expected to be significantly reduced.

Several waste management activities, such as recycling and composting, are part of community empowerment in waste management. These community empowerment efforts are expected to create new economic opportunities for the community in generating added value in waste management. Thus, community-based waste management is expected to create a clean, healthy, and sustainable environment.

3. Conclusion

Community empowerment can be chosen as a strategy in waste management. Various waste management programs are designed with community involvement as part of community empowerment efforts. Community empowerment efforts can be carried out by strengthening various community-based waste management facilities, such as waste banks, 3R waste collection sites, and so on.

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